

Rutin Revisited: A Comprehensive Review of Its Pharmacological Properties, Analytical Advances, and Novel Formulation Strategies

Sangeetha Jayaraman*¹, Samiksha Mallagoni¹, Geetha Jummidi¹

¹Department of Pharmacognosy, Malla Reddy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Maisammaguda, Dhulapally, Kompally, Secunderabad, Telangana – 500100, India.

Corresponding Author

Sangeetha Jayaraman

Abstract

Rutin, a naturally occurring flavonoid glycoside, has garnered significant attention due to its wide-ranging pharmacological properties, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, cardioprotective, and antimicrobial effects. Despite its therapeutic promise, clinical applications of rutin are limited by poor water solubility and low bioavailability. This review consolidates current research on analytical methods, such as HPLC, HPTLC, and UV-Vis spectroscopy, for rutin quantification, and highlights strategies to enhance its efficacy through nanotechnology and prodrug development. Novel formulations like rutin-loaded nanocrystals, silver nanoparticles, and Eudragit S100 nanospheres have demonstrated improved solubility, targeted delivery, and enhanced bioactivity *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Additionally, studies employing network pharmacology, molecular docking, and animal models reveal rutin's mechanisms in combating inflammation, nephropathy, ulcerative colitis, liver fibrosis, schistosomiasis, and cancer. Emerging evidence also supports the use of rutin in wound healing and transdermal applications. Collectively, these findings underscore rutin's potential as a multifunctional therapeutic agent and encourage further research for its clinical translation.

Keywords: Rutin, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, analytical methods, novel formulation.

Introduction

Rutin is a naturally occurring flavonoid glycoside, chemically known as quercetin-3-O-rutinoside, widely distributed in various fruits, vegetables, and medicinal plants such as buckwheat, citrus peels, and rue leaves.[1,2] Recognized for its potent antioxidant and radical-scavenging properties, rutin exhibits a broad spectrum of pharmacological activities, including anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, neuroprotective, hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, antimicrobial, and anticancer effects.[1,3] These diverse bioactivities are attributed to its ability to nephroprotective, modulate oxidative stress, inflammatory pathways, and cellular signaling

mechanisms.[4] Despite its therapeutic potential, rutin's clinical application is limited by low bioavailability due to poor absorption and rapid metabolism.[4-6] Ongoing research focuses on enhancing its pharmacokinetic profile and exploring its role in the prevention and management of various chronic diseases.

Importance of Rutin in Pharmaceutical and Nutraceutical Fields

Rutin, a bioflavonoid abundantly present in buckwheat, citrus fruits, apples, and various medicinal plants, holds significant importance in both pharmaceutical and nutraceutical domains due to its wide-ranging therapeutic properties and natural origin. In the pharmaceutical field, rutin has attracted attention for its potent antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antihypertensive, cardioprotective, neuroprotective, and anticancer activities. It modulates key cellular signaling pathways such as NF- κ B, MAPK, and PI3K/Akt, [7] offering potential in the treatment and management of chronic and degenerative diseases. Furthermore, its ability to strengthen capillaries and reduce vascular permeability has led to its incorporation into treatments for venous insufficiency and hemorrhoidal disorders.

In the nutraceutical industry, rutin is widely valued for its role in preventive health. As a functional dietary supplement, it contributes to maintaining vascular health, enhancing immune function, and reducing oxidative stress. [8] Due to its natural origin and favorable safety profile, rutin is increasingly formulated into tablets, capsules, and functional beverages. Recent advancements in drug delivery systems, including nanoformulations and encapsulation techniques, have improved its bioavailability, further broadening its application scope.

Overall, rutin bridges the gap between nutrition and medicine, offering a multifunctional compound that supports both disease prevention and therapeutic intervention, thus underlining its growing relevance in modern healthcare systems.

Phytochemistry of Rutin

Chemical structure

Rutin is a flavonoid also known by several other names, including 3-Rhamnosyl-glucosyl quercetin, Quercetin-3-rutinoside, Quercetin, 3-rhamnosyl-glucosyl, Rutoside, and Rutin hydrate. It has the molecular formula $C_{27}H_{30}O_{16}$ and its IUPAC name is: *2-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-5,7-dihydroxy-3-[(2S,3R,4S,5S,6R)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-[[[(2R,3R,4R,5R,6S)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-methyloxan-2-yl]oxymethyl]oxan-2-yl]oxychromen-4-one*. [9]

Fig.No.1: Structure of Rutin or Quercetin – 3 – rutinoside. [9]

Natural Occurrence in Plants

Rutin is a naturally occurring flavonoid glycoside, specifically the combination of the flavonol quercetin and the disaccharide rutinose. It is widely distributed across the plant kingdom and is found in a variety of fruits, vegetables, and medicinal herbs.[3] Rutin is abundant in citrus fruits (such as oranges and lemons), with especially high concentrations in the peels they contain between 32–49 mg/g of flavonoids expressed as rutin equivalents. Citrus leaves can have rutin concentrations as high as 11 g/kg in orange trees and 7 g/kg in lime trees.[10] Berries and apples are also notable sources.[11] Asparagus and buckwheat are significant sources. Buckwheat, in particular, is recognized for its high rutin content.[11,12] The name "rutin" is derived from *Ruta graveolens* (commonly known as rue), a plant rich in this compound. Other medicinal plants, such as *Morus alba* (mulberry) and *Carpobrotus edulis*, also contain rutin.[2,3] Rutin is present in tea, red wine, onions, and some members of the Lythraceae family (e.g., *Punica granatum* bark).[13]

Plant Source	Notable Content/Notes
Buckwheat	High rutin content
Citrus fruits (peels)	32–49 mg/g rutin equivalents
Citrus leaves	Up to 11 g/kg (orange), 7 g/kg (lime)
Apples, berries	Significant sources
Asparagus	Contains rutin
Tea, red wine	Present in beverages
<i>Ruta graveolens</i>	Eponymous plant, high rutin
<i>Morus alba</i> (mulberry)	Notable source
<i>Punica granatum</i> (bark)	High content in Lythraceae family

Table No. 1: Key Plant Sources of Rutin.[13]

Physicochemical properties

Rutin typically appears as a yellowish powder or pale yellow crystals and is characterized by its poor solubility in water, with reported values around 12.5–13 mg per 100 mL.[2,14] It dissolves more readily in organic solvents such as pyridine and ethanol.[14] Rutin's pKa value is reported as 6.17 in some studies and 4.3 in others, depending on the solvent and conditions, but it is generally considered a weak acid.[14,15] Physicochemically, rutin is highly hydrophilic under alkaline conditions due to its strong negative charge, but it remains only slightly hydrophilic and uncharged in acidic environments, which contributes to its low solubility in water and limits its absorption and bioavailability.[15] Rutin is stable in solid form but can degrade in solution, especially under light and heat. It is commonly encapsulated in nanoliposomes to enhance its stability and control its release for pharmaceutical applications.[16]. Because of its poor water solubility and low bioavailability, various formulation strategies, such as acetylation or encapsulation in nanoemulsions, have been explored to enhance its solubility and stability for pharmaceutical applications. As a dietary flavonoid, rutin is metabolized by gut microflora, which hydrolyzes it to its aglycone quercetin and sugar residues.[15]

Property	Value/Description
Molecular formula	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ O ₁₆
Molar mass	610.521 g/mol
Appearance	Yellowish powder/solid
Melting point	125 °C
Water solubility	12.5–13 mg/100 mL (125 mg/L)
Solubility in pyridine	Readily soluble
Solubility in ethanol	Soluble
pKa	6.17

Table No. 2: Summary of the Physicochemical Properties of Rutin

Analytical Techniques for Rutin Estimation

UV Analysis

A simple UV spectrophotometric method to evaluate the release of poorly water-soluble rutin from tablet dosage forms was studied. The optimal dissolution medium was found to be phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) containing 3% sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS), which enabled nearly 100% drug release within 55 minutes. The method demonstrated good linearity, precision, accuracy, and selectivity within the 0.04–0.1 mg/mL concentration range. The validated method is reliable, easy to perform, and suitable for routine quality control, with potential for adoption by official pharmacopeias. [17] Simultaneous quantification of Rutin and Curcumin in bulk powder and topical formulations, targeting conditions like Stasis dermatitis was carried out with UV spectrophotometric method. Using methanol as the solvent, optimal absorption was observed at 257 nm for Rutin and 422 nm for Curcumin. Validated according to ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines, the method met criteria for linearity, precision, accuracy, repeatability, LOD, LOQ, robustness, and ruggedness. The study concludes that the developed UV method is effective, reliable, and suitable for routine quality control of Rutin and Curcumin in pharmaceutical applications. [18]

This study aimed to enhance the water solubility and dissolution of rutin by synthesizing a more soluble hexaacetylated ester derivative. Through selective partial acetylation, the novel derivative demonstrated approximately two-fold improvement in solubility and dissolution compared to native rutin, potentially enhancing oral bioavailability. A validated UV/Vis spectrophotometric method was used for quantification, proving to be linear, accurate, precise, and robust at low concentrations (0.0259 mg/mL). Importantly, the antioxidant activity of the derivative remained comparable to that of rutin. Overall, the improved solubility and dissolution profile make this derivative promising for use in herbal and pharmaceutical formulations. [19]

HPLC Analysis

Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for identifying and quantifying key flavonoids—primarily quercetin and rutin—in mulberry (*Morus* spp.) leaf extract. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a Shimadzu LC system with a C18 column and UV detection at 259 nm. An isocratic elution with acetonitrile and 0.1% glacial acetic acid was used, with a 10-minute runtime at 37 °C. [20] Another study aimed for the separation and quantification of rutin and quercetin in buckwheat. Optimal analytical conditions included a mobile phase of methanol and methanol:water:acetic acid (100:150:5), a flow rate of 1.3 ml/min, and a column temperature of 30 °C. Both the methods demonstrated excellent linearity, accuracy, precision, repeatability, robustness, and acceptable LOD and LOQ values for both quercetin and rutin. [21]

HPLC method for the estimation of rutin in *Prosopis cineraria* was performed using a C18 column with a mobile phase of methanol and 0.05% formic acid (80:20) at pH 3.2 and a flow rate of 1 mL/min. Rutin showed a retention time of 5.7 minutes, with detection at 281 nm using a PDA detector. The method exhibited excellent linearity ($r^2 = 0.999$) over the range of 2–10 µg/mL, with sharp and symmetric peaks. Validation followed ICH guidelines, confirming the method's accuracy, precision, robustness, LOD, and LOQ. The method was successfully applied to quantify rutin in the crude extract of *Prosopis cineraria*, providing a reliable analytical tool for its assessment. [22]

HPTLC Analysis

Rutin from *Capparis zeylanica* (CZ) was isolated and evaluated using a newly developed high-performance thin-layer chromatography (HPTLC) method. This method is simple, sensitive, precise, accurate, and specific, employing silica gel 60 F254 as the stationary phase and a mobile phase of ethyl acetate–glacial acetic acid–formic acid–water (10:1.1:1.1:2.6, v/v). Rutin detection was carried out under UV light at 264 nm. The method exhibited linear calibration between 400–1400 ng/spot ($R^2 = 0.9953 \pm 0.0004$), with an RF value of 0.418 ± 0.004 , a LOD of 14.10 ng/spot, and a LOQ of 42.73 ng/spot. Validation studies confirmed compliance with ICH guidelines. [23] The identification and quantification of rutin in the methanolic leaf extracts of *Morus alba* L., *Morus nigra* L., and *Morus indica* L. (family: Moraceae) by novel HPTLC method. The separation was performed on silica gel 60 F254 plates using an optimized mobile phase of ethyl acetate: ethyl methyl ketone: formic acid: water (10:6:1:2, v/v/v/v). Densitometric scanning was done at 363 nm after derivatization with anisaldehyde sulphuric acid. The method followed ICH guidelines for precision, accuracy, and reproducibility and validated. [24]

ANTARTH capsules, a polyherbal formulation used for the development and validation a novel HPTLC method for the simultaneous estimation of quercetin, berberine, rutin, and curcumin. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a mobile phase of toluene:ethyl acetate:methanol:formic acid (5:3:2:0.5, v/v), with UV–VIS detection at 366 nm and 426 nm. The method demonstrated strong linearity with correlation coefficients above 0.997 for all analytes. The validated method was accurate, precise, and robustness. [25]

Rutin as Prodrug

Two novel bioconjugates—rutin oleate (RUT-O) and rutin linoleate (RUT-L)—were synthesized via enzymatic esterification with oleic acid (OA) and linoleic acid (LA), respectively, using Novozyme® 435. Their structures were confirmed by RAMAN and FT-IR spectroscopy. Toxicological evaluations in 2D cell lines (H9c2(2-1), HepaRG, HaCaT), 3D human epidermis models (EpiDerm™), and chick chorioallantoic membranes revealed that RUT-O showed dose-dependent cytotoxicity at 100 μ M, while RUT-L exhibited no cytotoxic effects across tested concentrations. Both conjugates impaired HepaRG cell migration at 25 μ M and demonstrated no irritant potential at 100 μ M. Computational analyses indicated increased lipophilicity but decreased solubility and drug-likeness compared to parent compounds. Overall, RUT-L displayed a favorable toxicological and pharmacological profile, suggesting its potential as a safer and more effective rutin-based therapeutic candidate. [26]

Biological Activities of Rutin

Anti-inflammatory activity

Rutin against drug-induced nephropathy using modern computational approaches such as network pharmacology and molecular docking explored. Drug-induced nephropathy-related genes and rutin-associated targets were identified through multiple databases, including DAVID, Swiss Target Prediction, STRING, Gene Cards, OMIM, Pub Chem, and Venn analysis. The intersecting targets were analyzed to construct a protein–protein interaction (PPI) network, revealing key molecular targets. KEGG pathway enrichment identified several critical genes—such as TNF, EGFR, TP53, PTGS2, PRKCA, and MMP9—implicated in nephrotoxicity. Fourteen major signaling pathways were found to play significant roles in mediating rutin's nephroprotective effects. The findings suggest that rutin may mitigate drug-induced kidney damage by modulating proinflammatory and metabolic pathways, highlighting its potential as a natural therapeutic agent. [27] Rutin-based mouthwash was developed and investigated its anti-inflammatory potential in comparison with a commercially available diclofenac sodium mouthwash. Two in vitro anti-inflammatory assays were employed: the bovine serum albumin (BSA) denaturation assay and the egg albumin denaturation assay. Results demonstrated that the rutin mouthwash exhibited comparable anti-inflammatory activity to the diclofenac sodium formulation. Both formulations showed a dose-dependent inhibition of protein denaturation across concentrations ranging from 10 to 50 μ L, with no statistically significant difference observed ($p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that the rutin-based mouthwash offers effective anti-inflammatory properties and may serve as a natural alternative to conventional formulations. [28]

This study compares the antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antithrombotic effects of rutin and its enzymatically synthesized glycoside derivatives (rutin mono- and di-glucosides) in both in vitro and in vivo models. Rutin glycosides demonstrated superior antioxidant activity and lower cytotoxicity in RAW264.7 macrophages compared to rutin. Both compounds similarly inhibited inflammatory mediators (NO, PGE₂, TNF- α , IL-6) and reduced platelet aggregation in vitro. They also prolonged prothrombin time (PT) and activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) in vitro, but not in vivo. Overall, while rutin glycosides showed improved safety and antioxidant capacity, both compounds exhibited comparable anti-inflammatory and antiplatelet effects. [29] The anti-inflammatory effects of three flavonoids—rutin, quercetin, and hesperidin—were evaluated in rats. Administered intraperitoneally at a dose of 80 mg/kg/day, all three compounds significantly inhibited inflammation in both phases. Among them, rutin demonstrated the strongest activity, particularly during the chronic phase, highlighting its potential as an effective natural anti-inflammatory agent. [30] Another study demonstrated combined anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects of quercetin and rutin in the proprietary formulation SophorOx™ in exercised Sprague–Dawley rats. Results showed that SophorOx™ was well-tolerated, with no adverse effects or significant changes in body weight, feed intake, liver function, or blood glucose. Importantly, treated rats exhibited a significant reduction in inflammatory and oxidative stress markers, including CRP, 8-OHdG, MDA, 8-iso-PGF₂ α , IL-1 β , and IL-6, compared to the exercise-only group. These findings suggest that the quercetin–rutin combination in SophorOx™ effectively mitigates exercise-induced oxidative and inflammatory stress. [31]

Anti-inflammatory effects in lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-stimulated RAW 264.7 macrophage cells demonstrated that rutin significantly reduced the expression of pro-inflammatory markers, including inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), TLR4, MyD88, TRAF6, and p65, while increasing I κ B expression. It also inhibited the phosphorylation of I κ B and p65 proteins. These findings suggest that rutin exerts its anti-inflammatory effects by modulating the TLR4/MyD88/NF- κ B signaling pathway, highlighting its potential as an adjuvant therapy for inflammatory diseases. [32] Rutin from garlic, its effect on anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory activity, in *S. mansoni* - infected mice were studied. Compared to PZQ, rutin significantly reduced liver pathology, likely by decreasing egg deposition and modulating proinflammatory cytokine levels involved in granuloma formation. These findings suggest that rutin possesses potent anti-schistosomal activity and may serve as a promising candidate for adjunct or alternative therapy. [33]

Effects of rutin (RUT) in a rat model of trinitrobenzene sulfonic acid (TNBS)-induced ulcerative colitis was evaluated with rutin administered before or after colitis induction. TNBS caused significant oxidative stress, inflammation, and tissue damage, evidenced by increased levels of proinflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β), lipid peroxidation, and myeloperoxidase (MPO), along with decreased antioxidant enzyme activities. Rutin treatment effectively reversed these effects by restoring antioxidant enzyme levels (GPx, SOD, CAT, GST), increasing nitric oxide (NO), and reducing inflammatory markers. These findings suggest that rutin promotes healing in ulcerative colitis through its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. [34] Another study evaluated the phytochemical composition and in vitro anti-inflammatory activity of the aerial parts of *Tridax procumbens* L. FT-IR and UV-Visible analyses confirmed functional groups, while HPLC quantified phenolic and flavonoid content, with ferulic acid, quercetin, and rutin among the key constituents. Anti-inflammatory activity was assessed using HRBC membrane

stabilization, protein denaturation, and proteinase inhibition assays across five concentrations (20–100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ extract showed the highest activity, comparable to aspirin. These effects are likely attributed to the plant's rich phenolic and flavonoid content. [35] *Desmodium molliculum* (EDM) leaves, in a rat model of carrageenan-induced acute inflammation, EDM was administered orally at doses of 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg. Both doses significantly reduced paw edema compared to the control group, with the most notable effects observed at 240 minutes post-induction. These findings confirm the anti-inflammatory potential of *Desmodium molliculum*, supporting its traditional use in managing inflammation. [36]

Comparative assessments using carrageenin- and formalin-induced edema, adjuvant arthritis, and cotton pellet granuloma models showed similar drug responses in both rats and mice when treated with prednisolone and indomethacin. Further dose-response studies with various anti-inflammatory agents revealed consistent inhibitory effects across tests, except for flufenamic acid, which was ineffective in some models. Cyproheptadine selectively inhibited formalin- and serotonin-induced edema. These findings support the use of mice as a valid and reliable model for anti-inflammatory drug screening. [37] Further study of synergistic anti-inflammatory effects of the flavonoids quercetin and rutin in combination with diclofenac in vivo rat models of carrageenan-induced paw edema, staircase climbing, and motility tests, the results showed that quercetin and rutin both had significant anti-inflammatory activity individually. However, their combination produced effects comparable to diclofenac, indicating a strong synergistic action. These findings support the potential of quercetin and rutin, particularly in combination, as effective alternative or complementary therapies for inflammatory disorders. [38]

Anti-diabetic activity

The effects of oral rutin, metformin, and their combination on blood glucose, lipid levels, and vascular function in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats showed significant improved blood glucose, total cholesterol, and triglyceride levels compared to untreated diabetic rats. Vascular function, accessed via aortic ring responses, showed that diabetic rats had heightened contraction to phenylephrine and impaired relaxation to acetylcholine and sodium nitroprusside. Combination therapy with rutin and metformin most effectively reduced abnormal contractions and improved relaxation responses, outperforming either treatment alone. Histological analysis of the pancreas, liver, and kidney also revealed the greatest improvements with combination therapy. In conclusion, combining rutin and metformin offers superior benefits for restoring metabolic and vascular health in diabetic rats compared to either agent alone. [39]

One more study on anti-diabetic potential of whole unripe jackfruit, identifying the dietary flavonoid rutin as a key active compound. Rutin demonstrated strong inhibitory activity against α -glucosidase, α -amylase, aldose reductase, and protein glycation, all relevant to diabetes progression. It acted competitively against α -glucosidase and α -amylase and non-competitively against aldose reductase, with low IC_{50} and K_i values. Molecular docking and simulation studies confirmed its strong and stable binding to the enzymes' active sites. These findings highlight rutin as a promising natural lead compound for developing effective anti-diabetic therapies. [40]

Oral administration of rutin (50 and 100 mg/kg) and pioglitazone (10 mg/kg) for three weeks significantly improved key diabetic markers in high-fat diet and streptozotocin-induced type 2 diabetic rats. Rutin lowered plasma glucose, glycosylated hemoglobin, and pro-inflammatory

cytokines (IL-6, TNF- α), while restoring liver antioxidant levels and serum lipid profile. It also improved pancreatic islet architecture and reversed liver cell hypertrophy. These results suggest that rutin exerts antidiabetic effects by modulating inflammation, oxidative stress, and lipid metabolism, and could serve as a complementary therapy alongside standard antidiabetic drugs. Clinical studies are needed to confirm these effects in humans. [41] The insulin-mimetic potential of rutin trihydrate and metformin using molecular docking simulations was evaluated. The 3D structures of both compounds were retrieved from PubChem, and docking was performed with the insulin receptor protein (1IR3) using AutoDock Vina, followed by visualization with Discovery Studio. Results showed that rutin trihydrate exhibited a higher binding affinity to the active site of 1IR3 compared to metformin, suggesting its potential as a more effective insulin mimic. These findings support rutin trihydrate as a promising candidate for further development in anti-diabetic therapies. [42]

Antihyperglycaemic and antioxidant effects of rutin, a dietary flavonoid, in normal and streptozotocin-induced diabetic Wistar rats for 45 days studied shows significant decrease in fasting plasma glucose, glycosylated hemoglobin, and oxidative stress markers, while increasing insulin, C-peptide, total hemoglobin, and non-enzymic antioxidant levels in diabetic rats. Rutin had no significant effects in normal rats. These findings indicate that rutin effectively improves glucose regulation and antioxidant status, supporting its potential as a therapeutic agent in diabetes management. [43]

Evaluation of antidiabetic effects of rutin from tartary buckwheat in diabetic mice, focusing on its role in gut microbiota regulation was studied. Oral administration of rutin significantly lowered blood glucose, improved lipid profiles, reduced inflammatory markers (TNF- α , IL-6), and increased insulin levels. Importantly, rutin also alleviated colon lesions and corrected gut microbiota dysbiosis by enriching beneficial bacteria like Akkermansia, Alistipes, and Roseburia, while reducing harmful microbes such as Escherichia and Mucispirillum. These findings suggest that rutin may ameliorate diabetes and its complications by modulating the gut microbiota. [44] The protective effects of rutin (Rtn) against methylglyoxal (MG)-induced oxidative stress in isolated pancreatic islets from mice investigated. MG exposure reduced insulin secretion and antioxidant enzyme activity, while increasing lipid peroxidation (MDA levels) in both normal and high-glucose conditions. Treatment with rutin (1–2 μ M) significantly restored insulin levels, reduced MDA, and enhanced antioxidant enzyme activities (catalase, SOD, GPx). These results suggest that rutin effectively protects pancreatic β -cells from oxidative damage and may support insulin function in diabetic conditions. [45]

The study explored the α -glucosidase inhibitory potential of compounds isolated from *Syzygium cumini* var. album, using ethanol extraction and chromatographic techniques. In vitro assays and molecular docking revealed that rutin exhibited a binding affinity and inhibitory activity comparable to acarbose, a standard anti-diabetic drug, with an IC₅₀ of 48.36 μ g/mL. These findings suggest that rutin from *S. cumini* may serve as a promising natural α -glucosidase inhibitor for diabetes management with potentially fewer side effects. [46] Further the effects of Rutin on diabetic nephropathy through both in vitro and in vivo approaches, focusing on its interaction with the nitric oxide (NO) pathway explored. In vitro experiments using human renal glomerular endothelial cells (HRGECs) showed that Rutin reduced high glucose-induced cell death and improved protein clearance. In vivo, Rutin administration in diabetic rats alleviated

kidney damage, lowered serum and urinary markers of nephropathy, and increased nitrite/nitrate levels and kidney collagen content in a dose-dependent manner. Histological analysis indicated improved kidney structure, with high doses of Rutin enhancing eNOS expression while reducing iNOS and nNOS levels. These findings suggest that Rutin, alongside L-Arginine, may offer therapeutic benefits for diabetic nephropathy by modulating the NO pathway. [47]

Hepatoprotective activity

The protective mechanisms of rutin and its aglycone quercetin against carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced liver damage in mice investigated. Both flavonoids reduced liver injury markers (ALT, AST) and improved liver histology. Quercetin more effectively preserved antioxidant enzyme activity (Cu/Zn SOD) and reduced fibrosis-related TGF-β1 expression, while rutin more strongly suppressed nitrosative stress and iNOS expression. Both compounds attenuated inflammation by down regulating NF-κB, TNF-α, and COX-2 and upregulated the antioxidant defense proteins Nrf2 and HO-1, with rutin showing greater efficacy at equivalent doses. These results suggest that while quercetin offers stronger antioxidant and antifibrotic benefits, rutin provides superior protection against nitrosative liver damage. [48] Further subcritical fluid-assisted extract of *Arctium tomentosum* Mill. root explored for phenolic profile, including notable compounds like chlorogenic acid and acacetin 7-O-glucoside, was analyzed using spectrophotometry and HPLC methods. In vitro assays (DPPH and FRAP) confirmed its strong antioxidant activity. In vivo, using a CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity model in mice, the extract demonstrated a dose-dependent hepatoprotective effect, reflected by improved plasma protein levels, reduced transaminase activities (ALAT, ASAT, GGT), and partial restoration of liver antioxidant enzymes (GPx, CAT, SOD). Histological analysis showed reduced liver damage. [49]

Rutin (RUT) against vortioxetine (VORTX)-induced hepatotoxicity in rats treated with varying doses of VORTX (28 mg/kg and 80 mg/kg), with or without co-administration of RUT (25 mg/kg), over 30 days. Liver function markers, oxidative stress biomarkers, DNA fragmentation, and liver histopathology were assessed. Results showed that RUT significantly mitigated VORTX-induced liver damage, improving levels of AST, ALT, LDH, MDA, SOD, GSH, GST, and other biomarkers. Histopathological analysis supported these findings. [50]

Calamus rotang (CR) ethyl acetate extract (350 mg/kg) when treated to CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity rats, its histopathological and immune histochemical analyses revealed that CR extract significantly suppressed pro-inflammatory markers (TNF-α, arginase, PPAR-α) and enhanced the antiapoptotic protein Bcl-2. HPLC profiling identified 14 polyphenols, with naringin, rutin, 7-hydroxy flavone, and ellagic acid showing strong antiapoptotic potential against BH3 protein via molecular docking. Overall, the CR extract demonstrated potent hepatoprotective activity through its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-steatosis, and antiapoptotic mechanisms. [51]

Anticancer activity

The potential of Naringin and Rutin to modulate the DNA damage response (DDR) pathway in cancer therapy by targeting key DDR proteins (PARP-1, ATM, ATR, CHK1, WEE1) through in

silico docking and in vitro experiments demonstrated strong binding affinities for DDR proteins and showed selective cytotoxicity against MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells while sparing normal fibroblasts. Comet assays confirmed targeted DNA damage in cancer cells. Both compounds also exhibited notable antioxidant activity, reducing oxidative stress. Despite promising ADMET profiles, optimization is needed to enhance therapeutic potential. [52] Further studies on successfully isolated rutin from *Citrus reticulata* and *Citrus limon* revealed significant antioxidant and anticancer activities, with *C. reticulata*-derived rutin showing higher potency and yield. The antioxidant activity ranged from 31.64 to 76.28 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, while anticancer activity (IC_{50}) ranged from 4 to 7 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, close to the standard drug doxorubicin ($\text{IC}_{50} = 3 \mu\text{g/mL}$). The findings highlight *C. reticulata* as a richer source of bioactive rutin, supporting its potential as a natural therapeutic agent, particularly against lung cancer. [53]

Antimutagenic effects were assessed using the Ames test, while antioxidant potential was evaluated through several in vitro assays such as DPPH, lipid peroxidation, deoxyribose degradation, reducing power, and metal chelation. Rutin demonstrated strong free radical scavenging and mutation-inhibiting capabilities, highlighting its potential as a therapeutic agent. [54]

Neuroprotective activity

Aluminum chloride (AlCl_3)-induced toxicity in *Drosophila melanogaster*, a model for neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's disease used to establish the protective effects of rutin. Flies exposed to AlCl_3 showed reduced survival, impaired locomotion, decreased antioxidant enzyme activity (SOD, CAT), and increased oxidative stress (MDA) and acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity. Co-treatment with rutin (0.5 and 1 mg/kg) significantly reversed these effects, indicating improved antioxidant defense and neuroprotection. These results suggest that rutin may serve as a promising therapeutic agent against aluminum-induced neurotoxicity and related disorders due to its antioxidant and anticholinesterase properties. [55]

Antioxidant activity

An enzymatic method to synthesize rutin oleate a lipophilic ester of rutin using oleic acid and Novozym 435 as the catalyst developed. The product was confirmed through FTIR, HPLC-MS, and NMR analyses, identifying the esterification site at the 4''-OH of the rhamnose group. The process achieved over 93% conversion in 48 hours. Rutin oleate showed comparable antioxidant activity to standard antioxidants at 60°C, and superior performance at 120°C, highlighting its potential as a novel, heat-stable antioxidant for application in oil- and fat-based foods. [56] Another study with a successful synthesis of a rutin- β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) inclusion complex ($[\text{Rut}\subset\beta\text{-CD}]$), confirmed by FT-IR and DSC analyses. The complexation significantly enhanced rutin's antioxidant activity, as indicated by a reduced EC_{50} value in the DPPH assay. Quantum chemical calculations using the GFN2-xTB method demonstrated that solvent type affects the structural stability and interaction energy of the complex, with the strongest interaction observed in water, followed by ethanol and dimethyl sulfoxide. The results highlight the potential of β -CD to improve rutin's bioactivity and solubility through inclusion complex formation. [57]

Antiviral activity

Authors evaluated the antiviral potential of Rutin against Equine Hepacivirus-8 (EqHV-8) through in vitro and in vivo experiments. Rutin effectively inhibited EqHV-8 replication at various stages of its life cycle, primarily via activation of the Nrf2/HO-1 antioxidant pathway. In vivo mouse model results further confirmed Rutin's ability to reduce viral infection in lung tissue. These findings suggest that Rutin is a promising therapeutic agent for managing EqHV-8 infections. [58]

Formulation & Delivery Systems

Rutin nanocrystals were developed using various stabilizers, with hydroxypropyl beta-cyclodextrin (HP- β -CD) yielding the most favorable results. These nanocrystals exhibited improved particle size, stability, drug entrapment, and photostability. Compared to free drug formulations, HP- β -CD-stabilized nanocrystals significantly enhanced rutin's solubility (up to 202-fold), dissolution rate (up to 6.7-fold), and skin permeability (2.5-fold increase). In vivo studies confirmed superior anti-inflammatory activity in a rat paw edema model compared to both free rutin and commercial diclofenac gel. This formulation presents a promising strategy for improving the therapeutic efficacy of rutin. [59] A novel nanomedicine—ZIF-8@Rutin—was developed by loading the flavonoid rutin into a zeolitic imidazolate framework-8 (ZIF-8) via electrostatic adsorption. Characterization confirmed successful synthesis, and the nanocomposite demonstrated strong antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, along with notable anti-inflammatory effects through macrophage polarization. In vivo studies showed that ZIF-8@Rutin effectively reduced inflammation and accelerated wound healing, with good cytocompatibility. These findings suggest ZIF-8@Rutin is a promising multifunctional agent for treating infected wounds. [60]

Another study employed a Quality by Design (QbD) approach to develop and optimize rutin-loaded silver nanoparticles, aiming to enhance its therapeutic potential. Among 15 formulations, F12 was identified as optimal, with an average particle size of 126.3 nm and sustained drug release (97.3%). Characterization was performed using UV, FTIR, SEM, and DLS techniques. F12 showed improved water solubility and exhibited strong antioxidant and anticancer activity in G361 and MCF-7 cell lines. Additionally, F12 significantly reduced cyclophosphamide-induced micronuclei formation in mouse bone marrow, indicating notable anticlastogenic potential. These findings highlight rutin silver nanoparticles as a promising multifunctional therapeutic agent. [61]

To enhance the solubility and colon-targeted delivery of rutin for the treatment of colon carcinoma using pH-sensitive nanospheres formulated with Eudragit S100 via nanoprecipitation. Optimized formulations, varying in drug-to-polymer ratios and Poloxamer-188 concentrations, demonstrated high entrapment efficiency (94.19%–98.1%), nanometric size, and stable zeta potential (< -20 mV). In vitro studies confirmed improved aqueous solubility and colon-specific drug release. Rutin-loaded nanospheres exhibited over a twofold increase in cytotoxicity against HCT-116 colon cancer cells compared to free rutin, with minimal toxicity to normal fibroblasts. [62] An eco-friendly, bio-inspired synthesis of chitosan/copper oxide (CS-CuO) nano-composites using rutin as a reducing and stabilizing agent. The nanocomposites,

characterized by UV-Vis, FE-SEM, TEM, EDS, XRD, and FTIR, were spherical in shape with sizes ranging from 10–30 nm and displayed a monoclinic crystal structure. The FTIR and EDS analyses confirmed the involvement of rutin and chitosan in the synthesis process. The CS-CuO nanocomposites exhibited concentration-dependent anti-proliferative effects against A549 human lung cancer cells, with an IC₅₀ of $20 \pm 0.50 \mu\text{g/mL}$, and induced apoptosis as confirmed by AO/EtBr staining. These findings suggest their potential as anticancer agents in biomedical applications. [63]

Topical application of rutin-NPs significantly enhanced wound healing by reducing oxidative stress (restoring GSH, CAT, SOD; reducing MDA) and suppressing inflammation (lowering CRP, IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α), likely through Nrf2 activation. Molecular docking confirmed rutin's strong binding affinity to key inflammatory and oxidative stress-related proteins, supporting its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions. These findings highlight rutin-NPs as a promising topical agent for diabetic wound management. [64] Ultrasound as a physical method to enhance rutin's transdermal absorption and therapeutic efficacy investigated. In vitro diffusion studies identified optimal ultrasound settings (1 MHz and 3 MHz at 0.2 W/cm²) that significantly increased intradermal retention—up to 2.63 times more than without ultrasound. In vivo experiments using a tape-stripping model in mice confirmed that ultrasound-assisted delivery accelerated skin recovery and restored barrier function by day four. [65]

Conclusion

Recent advancements in the study of rutin have significantly expanded our understanding of its multifaceted pharmacological potential and analytical methodologies. As a naturally occurring flavonoid, rutin exhibits a wide spectrum of biological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, neuroprotective, and nephroprotective effects. Emerging research also underscores its role in modulating metabolic disorders, improving vascular health, and enhancing drug bioavailability when used in combination therapies. Innovative formulations and delivery systems—such as nanoparticles, liposomes, and inclusion complexes—have shown promise in overcoming rutin's limitations in solubility and bioavailability, thereby enhancing its therapeutic efficacy. Despite these encouraging findings, further clinical trials and mechanistic studies are essential to validate its safety, efficacy, and pharmacokinetics in humans. Overall, rutin remains a promising nutraceutical and pharmacological agent with significant potential for integration into modern therapeutic strategies.

REFERENCES

1. Islam, M. A., Mubarak, M. S., & Sultana, N. (2021). Rutin: Therapeutic potential and recent advances in drug delivery. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2021, 9913179. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9913179>
2. Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *Rutin*. Wikipedia. Retrieved June 9, 2025, from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rutin>
3. ScienceDirect. (n.d.). *Rutin - Medicine and Dentistry*. Retrieved June 9, 2025, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/medicine-and-dentistry/rutin>
4. Mahmoud, S. A. A., & Ali, H. A. (2024). Protective effect of rutin against cisplatin-induced nephrotoxicity in rats. *Menoufia Journal of Veterinary Medical Research*, 5(2),

341806.
https://mjvm.journals.ekb.eg/article_341806_d0c1f1a91ac4e7f93dfcea90a36e6b62.pdf
5. ScienceDirect. (n.d.). *Rutin - Pharmacology, Toxicology & Pharmaceutical Science*. Retrieved June 9, 2025, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/pharmacology-toxicology-and-pharmaceutical-science/rutin>
 6. Ganeshpurkar, A., & Saluja, A. K. (2017). The pharmacological potential of rutin. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, 25(2), 149–164. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5355559/>
 7. Xue, J.-C., Yuan, S., Meng, H., Hou, X.-T., Li, J., Zhang, H.-M., Chen, L.-L., Zhang, C.-H., & Zhang, Q.-G. (2023). The role and mechanism of flavonoid herbal natural products in ulcerative colitis. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 158, 114086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2022.114086>
 8. Prasad, R., & Prasad, S. B. (2019). A review on the chemistry and biological properties of Rutin, a promising nutraceutical agent. *Asian Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 5(S1), 1–20.
 9. National Center for Biotechnology Information. (2025). *PubChem Compound Summary for CID 5280805, Rutin*. Retrieved June 14, 2025, from <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Rutin>
 10. Singh, S. P., & Sashidhara, K. V. (2017). Lipid lowering agents of natural origin: An account of some promising chemotypes. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 140, 331–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2017.09.020>
 11. Mihanfar, A., Nouri, M., Roshangar, L., & Khadem-Ansari, M. H. (2021). Polyphenols: Natural compounds with promising potential in treating polycystic ovary syndrome. *Reproductive Biology*, 21(2), 100500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.repbio.2021.100500>
 12. Patel, K., & Patel, D. K. (2019). Chapter 26 – The beneficial role of rutin, a naturally occurring flavonoid in health promotion and disease prevention: A systematic review and update. In R. R. Watson & V. R. Preedy (Eds.), *Bioactive food as dietary interventions for arthritis and related inflammatory diseases* (2nd ed., pp. 457–479). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813820-5.00026-X>
 13. Mane, M. D., Patole, N. S., Kodalkar, V. N., & Metkari, S. A. (2024). An overview of antimicrobial properties of rutin. *International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Allied Sciences (IJRPAS)*, 3(2), 17–23.
 14. Doaa A. Madkour, Mohamed M. Ahmed, Ahmed F. Elkirdasy, Sahar H. Orabi, and Ahmed A. Mousa (2024). Rutin: Chemical properties, Pharmacokinetic properties and Biological activities. *MJVM*, Vol. (4), Issue (2), pages (26-34). DOI: 10.21608/mjvm.2024.341806
 15. Tobar-Delgado E, Mejía-España D, Osorio-Mora O, Serna-Cock L. Rutin: Family Farming Products' Extraction Sources, Industrial Applications and Current Trends in Biological Activity Protection. *Molecules*. 2023 Aug 3;28(15):5864. doi: 10.3390/molecules28155864. PMID: 37570834; PMCID: PMC10421072.
 16. Safarbalou, A., Haghipanah, M., Moradi-kor, N., Ramezani, E., Fakhr Hosseini, S. M., Taheri Roudsari, S. S., Sadat Afraz, E. Physicochemical properties of rutin loaded into nanoliposomes and its uses for the treatment of oral ulcers. *Eurasian Chemical Communications*, 2022; 4(3): 202-208. doi: 10.22034/ecc.2022.323333.1289

17. Abu Alhasan, M., Qutob, T., Obedat, S., Yahyia, D., & Watson, D. G. (2017). Dissolution method development and validation of rutin tablet. *Palestinian Medical and Pharmaceutical Journal*, 2(1), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.59049/2790-0231.1042>
18. Bhusannavar, D., Sharannavar, B., Darbha, N. S., Suryawanshi, S., Patil, S., & Bhandurge, P. (2024). Development and validation of UV-visible spectrophotometry method for simultaneous estimation of rutin and curcumin in bulk pharmaceuticals. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*, 14(3), 833–842. <https://doi.org/10.5530/ijpi.14.3.93>
19. Abualhasan, M., Assali, M., Jaradat, N., & Sarhan, T. (2019). Synthesis, formulation and analytical method validation of rutin derivative. *Letters in Drug Design & Discovery*, 16(6). <https://doi.org/10.2174/1570180816666181108114706>
20. Garg, S., Chahal, R., Kaushik, D., Kumar, R., & Mittal, V. (2023). RP-HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of rutin and quercetin in *Morus alba* L. leaf extract. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 16(5), 2327–2335. <https://doi.org/10.52711/0974-360X.2023.00383>
21. Jan, S., Ahmad, J., Dar, M. M., Wani, A. A., Tahir, I., & Kamili, A. N. (2022). Development and validation of a reverse phase HPLC-DAD method for separation, detection & quantification of rutin and quercetin in buckwheat (*Fagopyrum* spp.). *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 59(7), 2875–2883. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-021-05312-0>
22. Bishnoi, R. S., Kumar, M., Shukla, A. K., & Jain, C. (2018). Development and validation of novel HPLC method for the estimation of rutin in crude hydromethanolic leaf extract of *Prosopis cineraria*. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 8(6), 68–73. <https://jddtonline.info/index.php/jddt/article/view/2016>
23. Pawar, H., Ghule, B., Sahu, A., & et al. (2024). High-performance thin-layer chromatography method development and validation for quantification of rutin in different parts of *Capparis zeylanica* Linn. plant. *Journal of Planar Chromatography – Modern TLC*, 37(1), 137–149. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00764-024-00295-y>
24. Huria, N., Saraf, A., & Saraf, A. (2024). Estimation of rutin from *Morus* species using validated HPTLC method. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2(3), 565–577. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10954737>
25. Khairnar, A., Lohidasan, S., Dubey, R., & et al. (2023). Analytical method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of quercetin, berberine, rutin, and curcumin in a polyherbal formulation using high-performance thin-layer chromatography. *Journal of Planar Chromatography – Modern TLC*, 36(1), 63–70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00764-023-00221-8>
26. Dehelean, C. A., Coricovac, D., Pinzaru, I., Marcovici, I., Macasoi, I. G., Semenescu, A., Lazar, G., Cinta Pinzaru, S., Radulov, I., Alexa, E., & Cretu, O. (2022). Rutin bioconjugates as potential nutraceutical prodrugs: An in vitro and in ovo toxicological screening. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 13, Article 1000608. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.1000608>
27. Thakur, P., Mittal, N., Chaudhary, J., Kamboj, S., & Jain, A. (2025). Unveiling the substantial role of rutin in the management of drug-induced nephropathy using network pharmacology and molecular docking. *International Immunopharmacology*, 146, 113911. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intimp.2024.113911>

28. Sogasu, D., & Kumar, J. K. (2023). Comparative anti-inflammatory activity of rutin-based mouthwash and diclofenac sodium: An in-vitro evaluation. *Journal of Pioneering Medical Sciences*, 12(3), 61–64.
29. Choi, S. S., Park, H. R., & Lee, K. A. (2021). A comparative study of rutin and rutin glycoside: Antioxidant activity, anti-inflammatory effect, effect on platelet aggregation and blood coagulation. *Antioxidants*, 10(11), 1696. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10111696>
30. Guardia, T., Rotelli, A. E., Juarez, A. O., & Pelzer, L. E. (2001). Anti-inflammatory properties of plant flavonoids: Effects of rutin, quercetin and hesperidin on adjuvant arthritis in rat. *Il Farmaco*, 56(9), 683–687. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-827X\(01\)01111-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-827X(01)01111-9)
31. Shanmugasundaram, D., & Roza, J. M. (2024). Assessment of anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities of a proprietary preparation of quercetin–rutin blend (SophorOx™) in exercised rats. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2024, Article 9063936. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/9063936>
32. Tian, C., Liu, X., Chang, Y., Wang, R., Yang, M., & Liu, M. (2021). Rutin prevents inflammation induced by lipopolysaccharide in RAW 264.7 cells via conquering the TLR4-MyD88-TRAF6-NF-κB signalling pathway. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 73(1), 110–117. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpp/rgaa015>
33. Hamad, R. S. (2023). Rutin, a flavonoid compound derived from garlic, as a potential immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory agent against murine schistosomiasis mansoni. *Nutrients*, 15, 1206. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15051206>
34. Hussein, S. A., Abou Zaid, O. A. R., Abdel-Maksoud, H. A., & Akasha, K. A. A. (2014). Anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant effect of rutin on 2, 4, 6-trinitrobenzene sulfonic acid induced ulcerative colitis in rats. *Benha Veterinary Medical Journal*, 27(1), 208–220.
35. Kavitha, R., & Prasanna, G. (2018). Phytochemical screening and in vitro anti-inflammatory activity of aerial parts of *Tridax procumbens* L. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 50(2), 115–120.
36. Olascuaga-Castillo, K., Castillo-Medina, O., Villacorta-Zavaleta, M., et al. (2023). Phytochemical screening and anti-inflammatory activity of the extract from the leaves of *Desmodium molliculum* (Kunth) DC (Fabaceae) in rats with acute inflammation. *Pharmacognosy Journal*, 15(5), 786–790.
37. Sugishita, E., Amagaya, S., & Ogihara, Y. (1981). Anti-inflammatory testing methods: Comparative evaluation of mice and rats. *Journal of Pharmacobio-Dynamics*, 4(8), 565–575.
38. Kumbhar, P. S., Kumar, B., Gadad, A. P., Mane, S., Giri, S., Burli, S. C., & Shirguppe, A. (2024). In vivo synergistic anti-inflammatory action of rutin and quercetin using rat model. *International Journal of Medical Toxicology and Legal Medicine*, 27(2), 263–269. <https://ijmtlm.org/index.php/journal/article/view/219>
39. David, S. R., Lai, P. P. N., Chellian, J., et al. (2023). Influence of rutin and its combination with metformin on vascular functions in type 1 diabetes. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 12423. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-39442-6>
40. Maradesha, T., Patil, S. M., Phanindra, B., et al. (2022). Multiprotein inhibitory effect of dietary polyphenol rutin from whole green jackfruit flour targeting different stages of diabetes mellitus: Defining a bio-computational stratagem. *Separations*, 9, 262. <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations9090262>

41. Niture, N. T., Ansari, A. A., & Naik, S. R. (2014). Anti-hyperglycemic activity of rutin in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats: An effect mediated through cytokines, antioxidants and lipid biomarkers. *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*, 52(7), 720–727.
42. Tejaswini, R., & Praveen Kumar, I. (2025). Comparing the insulin mimetic activity of rutin trihydrate and metformin by using computational tools for antidiabetic assessment. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 3252, 020143.
43. Kamalakkannan, N., & Prince, P. S. M. (2006). Antihyperglycaemic and antioxidant effect of rutin, a polyphenolic flavonoid, in streptozotocin-induced diabetic Wistar rats. *Basic & Clinical Pharmacology & Toxicology*, 98(1), 97–103.
44. Cai, C., Cheng, W., Shi, T., et al. (2023). Rutin alleviates colon lesions and regulates gut microbiota in diabetic mice. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 4897. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31647-z>
45. Harooni, E., Radmehr, V., Razliqi, R. N., Ahangarpour, A., & Bazayar, H. (2025). Rutin protects pancreatic islets against methylglyoxal-induced oxidative stress and elevates insulin secretion. *Gazi Medical Journal*, 36(2), 177–183. <https://doi.org/10.12996/gmj.2024.4236>
46. Andhiarto, Y., Sukardiman, S., Suciati, S., Rosandy, A. R., Muslikh, F. A., & Riwanti, P. (2025). In silico and in vitro studies of rutin from *Syzygium cumini* (L.) Skeels. var. album as an antidiabetic α -glucosidase enzyme inhibitor. *Trends in Sciences*, 22(2), Article 9047. <https://doi.org/10.48048/tis.2025.9047>.
47. Manasa, P., & Suhasin, G. (2023). Nephroprotective activity of rutin in diabetic nephropathy rat model targeting nitric oxide pathway. *Journal of Drug and Alcohol Research*, 12(10).
48. Domitrović, R., Jakovac, H., Vasiljev Marchesi, V., et al. (2012). Differential hepatoprotective mechanisms of rutin and quercetin in CCl₄-intoxicated BALB/cN mice. *Acta Pharmacologica Sinica*, 33, 1260–1270. <https://doi.org/10.1038/aps.2012.62>
49. Aitynova, A., Sevastre, B., Ielciu, I., Hanganu, D., Olah, N.-K., Ibragimova, N., Shalakhmetova, T., Benedec, D., Lyu, M., Krasnoshtanov, A., et al. (2024). Hepatoprotective activity and oxidative stress reduction of an *Arctium tomentosum* Mill. root extract in mice with experimentally induced hepatotoxicity. *Livers*, 4(4), 696–710. <https://doi.org/10.3390/livers4040048>
50. Anwar, M. M., & Laila, I. M. I. (2024). The ameliorating effect of rutin on hepatotoxicity and inflammation induced by the daily administration of vortioxetine in rats. *BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies*, 24, 153. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-024-04447-9>
51. Anwar, W. S., Abdel-Maksoud, F. M., Sayed, A. M., et al. (2023). Potent hepatoprotective activity of common rattan (*Calamus rotang* L.) leaf extract and its molecular mechanism. *BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies*, 23, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-023-03853-9>
52. Pravin, B., Nanaware, V., Ashwini, B., et al. (2024). Assessing the antioxidant properties of naringin and rutin and investigating their oxidative DNA damage effects in breast cancer. *Scientific Reports*, 14, 15314. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-63498-7>
53. Tiwari, P., Mishra, R., Mazumder, R., Mazumder, A., & Singh, A. (2024). A study on anti-oxidant and anti-cancer perspectives of rutin. *Current Cancer Therapy Reviews*, 20(2), e190523217070. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1573394719666230519095551>

54. Thukral, A. (2015). Evaluation of antimutagenic and antioxidant activities of rutin. *International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences*, 6(1), 816–825.
55. Iyiegbu, M. E., & Enogieru, A. B. (2024). Antioxidant and anticholinesterase activity of rutin in aluminum chloride-exposed *Drosophila melanogaster*. *Comparative Clinical Pathology*, 33, 445–452. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00580-024-03564-8>
56. Liu, Y., Wang, Q., Liu, C., Yang, H., Jia, L., Zhao, L., Gong, F., Tan, C., Tao, H., & He, W.-S. (2023). Improved antioxidant activity of rutin via lipase-mediated esterification with oleic acid. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 103(7), 3489–3500.
57. Pham, T. L., Nguyen, T. T. H., Nguyen, T. A., Le-Deygen, I., Le, T. M. H., Vu, X. M., Le, H. K., Van, C. B., Usacheva, T. R., Mai, T. T., & Tran, D. L. (2024). Antioxidant activity of an inclusion complex between rutin and β -cyclodextrin: Experimental and quantum chemical studies. *RSC Advances*, 14, 18330–18342.
58. Chen, L., Li, S., Li, W., Yu, Y., Sun, Q., Chen, W., Zhou, H., Wang, C., Li, L., Xu, M., Khan, M. Z., Li, Y., & Wang, T. (2024). Rutin prevents EqHV-8 induced infection and oxidative stress via Nrf2/HO-1 signaling pathway. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, 14, 1386462. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2024.1386462>
59. Hassan, A. S., & Soliman, G. M. (2022). Rutin nanocrystals with enhanced anti-inflammatory activity: Preparation and ex vivo/in vivo evaluation in an inflammatory rat model. *Pharmaceutics*, 14(12), 2727. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics14122727>
60. Xia, X., Song, X., Li, Y., Hou, W., Lv, H., Li, F., Li, Y., Liu, J., & Li, X. (2022). Antibacterial and anti-inflammatory ZIF-8@Rutin nanocomposite as an efficient agent for accelerating infected wound healing. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 10, Article 1026743. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2022.1026743>
61. Yadha, H., et al. (2024). QbD approach for green synthesis of rutin silver nanoparticles – Screening for antioxidant, anticancer and anticlastogenic potential. *Heliyon*, 10(20), e38391.
62. Asfour, M. H., & Mohsen, A. M. (2017). Formulation and evaluation of pH-sensitive rutin nanospheres against colon carcinoma using HCT-116 cell line. *Journal of Advanced Research*, 9, 17–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2017.10.003>
63. Bharathi, D., Ranjithkumar, R., Chandarshekar, B., & Bhuvaneshwari, V. (2019). Bio-inspired synthesis of chitosan/copper oxide nanocomposite using rutin and their anti-proliferative activity in human lung cancer cells. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 141, 476–483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.08.235>
64. Naseeb, M., Albajri, E., Almasaudi, A., et al. (2024). Rutin promotes wound healing by inhibiting oxidative stress and inflammation in metformin-controlled diabetes in rats. *ACS Omega*, 9(30), 32394–32406. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.3c05595>
65. Yue, Q., He, B., Guo, Z., Zhang, N., Zhang, M., & Zhang, Y. (2025). Exploration of ultrasound-enhanced transdermal delivery efficiency and anti-inflammatory effect of rutin. *Pharmaceutics*, 18, 464. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph18040464>